

Investigation on ternary complex formation between maltol and dipeptides with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}; Potentiometric, synthetic and antibacterial studies

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Abstract : The formation constants of mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} with maltol (mal) and dipeptides viz. glycylglycine (GG), glycylvaline (GV), glycylleucine (GL) and glycylisoleucine (GIL) were determined pH metrically by employing algebraic method. The UV-Visible, IR and Mass spectra of isolated solid metal complexes of Ni^{II} inferred the formation of corresponding ternary complexes. The complexes have been screened for antibacterial activity and the results are compared with the activity of the free ligands. The observed increased antibacterial activity evident from these studies in ternary complexes than in corresponding free ligands suggests more lipophilicity of metal complexes to act on bacterial cell.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, M^{II}, potentiometric studies, stability constants, synthesis, spectral studies, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The study of mixed ligand complexes in biochemical systems is more extensive. The prominence of these complexes is evident from the fact that, a large number of biochemical reactions occur within the coordination sphere of metal ion. Hence it is worthwhile to investigate on their formation, stability, structure and on the mutual influence of two ligands bound to the same metal ion¹.

Small peptides containing 2–3 amino acid residues are constituent parts of proteins. The physiological roles they played in organisms and the binding properties with metal ions have been very attractive^{2,3}. The nature of metal ion binding of dipeptides in presence of maltol (3-hydroxy-2-methyl-4H-pyran-4-one) is of interest in view of the importance of maltol to control the level of metal ion content in biological systems^{4–7}. Hence in the present work, we have studied the formation of ternary complexes i.e. [M^{II}-(dipeptide)-(mal)] by potentiometric method and characterization of the corresponding synthesized solid Ni^{II} complexes by spectral methods.

Experimental

Materials :

Metal nitrates were obtained from Merck. The dipep-

tides viz. GG, GV, GL and GIL were obtained from SRL (India) and 'mal' from Sigma-Aldrich. Other reagents and solvents used were purified in the laboratory prior to use. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. Carbonate free NaOH was prepared and standardized by titrating with potassium hydrogen phthalate. Stock solutions of analytically pure metal nitrates were prepared and standardized volumetrically by known procedures⁸.

Methods :

Potentiometric measurements :

Potentiometric titrations were carried out using a Control dynamic pH meter with a combined glass electrode in the pH region 2–11. The pH meter was calibrated daily using standard buffer solutions (Merck) with pH values of 4.0, 7.0 and 9.2. All titrations were carried out in solutions contained in a 50 cm³ jacketed (double walled) cell, thermostatted at 303 K. The ionic strength of the solutions was kept constant (0.1 M) using KNO₃ solution. And a total volume of 50 ml in the cell was used for each titration. The potentiometric measurements were made for the following solutions (A = mal, L = dipeptide and M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}).

(a) 5 ml of 0.01 mmol ligand A or L + 5 ml of 1 M KNO₃ for the determination of proton dissociation constants of ligands.

(b) 5 ml of 0.01 mmol ligand A or L + 5 ml of 0.01 mmol M^{II} + 5 ml of 1 M KNO_3 for the determination of stability constants of 1 : 1 metal ligand complex (ML or MA complex).

(c) 5 ml of 0.01 mmol ligand A + 5 ml of 0.01 mmol ligand L + 5 ml of 0.01 mmol M^{II} + 5 ml of 1 M KNO_3 for the determination of stability constants of 1 : 1 : 1 metal ligand complex (MLA complex).

The contents were titrated with carbonate free NaOH (5×10^{-2} M) solution and pH measurements were made in aqueous medium. The contents were turned to green color while titrating with Ni^{II} , light pink color with Co^{II} and colorless in presence of Zn^{II} . The calculations of protonation constants of ligands and stability constants of binary and ternary complexes from potentiometric data were accomplished by using a computer program BEST⁹.

Synthesis of ternary complexes :

An aqueous solution of 5 ml nickel nitrate (1 mmol) was added to GG (1 mmol) dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water and stirred for 5 min. To this mixture, 'mal' (1 mmol) dissolved in 10 ml of methanol was added and followed by the addition of methanolic ammonia to adjust the solution pH 7–8 to facilitate the complex formation through deprotonation. Then the solution is refluxed for 1 h. After 2–3 days green colored complex was obtained^{10,11}. Ternary complexes of GV, GL and GIL were prepared by the similar method. These complexes were characterized by IR, UV-Vis and mass spectral data analyses.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra were recorded as KBr discs in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} with Tensor-27 (Bruker-optics) FTIR spectrophotometer.

ESI mass spectra :

ESI mass spectra of metal complexes were recorded using a liquid chromatography quadruple ion trap mass spectrometer (Thermo Finnigan, San Jose, CA, USA). All the spectra were recorded under identical experimental conditions, and are average of 20–25 scans. Stock (1 mM) solutions of compounds were diluted with HPLC-grade methanol to achieve a final concentration of 10 μ M each.

UV-Visible spectra :

UV-Visible spectra of the ligands and ternary com-

plexes were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2450 UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The spectra were recorded with 1×10^{-4} M ligand solutions in UV region, and ternary metal complexes spectra recorded in the UV and visible region with 1×10^{-4} M and 5×10^{-2} M solutions respectively. All the solutions of ligands and metal complexes were prepared in DMSO.

Antibacterial activity :

In vivo antibacterial activities of the ligands and metal complexes were determined by agar well diffusion method. The bacteria species used for this test include clinical sample of Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* [MTCC 2063], *Staphylococcus aureus* [MTCC 2901] and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* [MTCC 1652]. The nutrient agar was suspended in distilled water (1000 ml) and heated to boiling till it dissolved. The medium and petridishes were autoclaved at 15 psi for 20 min. To each petriplate, 20 ml of sterilized medium was added. After agar was set, 10 percent inoculums (suspension culture) was added to each petriplate and spread thoroughly by rotary motion of the plate. After inoculation, wells were scooped out with 7 mm sterile cork borer and to each cup 100 μ L of 1% test solution of ligand and metal complexes dissolved in DMSO were added. Cultures were kept in an incubator at 28 °C for 24 h. The antibacterial activities of the compounds were estimated on the basis of the size of the inhibition zone formed around the wells on sensitivity media.

Results and discussion

Potentiometric studies :

A set of identical titration curves are obtained for the different ternary systems under investigation. The protonation/proton dissociation constants (pKa) and the binary stability constants have been redetermined and were further refined using computer program 'BEST'. Results (Table 1) agree fairly well with the literature values. From the calculated values it is clear that the dipeptides show two pKa values, the highest pKa value corresponds to the deprotonation of NH_3^+ group and the lowest value is for the deprotonation of protonated acid group (in order to calculate the dissociation constant of acid group one proton is added to COO^-). The slight variation in the pKa values of dipeptides i.e. from GG to GIL can be assignable to the presence and increasing length of aliphatic chain. The single pKa value in case of 'mal' is attributable to the deprotonation of hydroxyl group. Titration curves of free ligand, binary and ternary systems of 'mal' (ligand

Table 1. Proton dissociation constants of free ligands and stability constants of binary and ternary metal complexesT = 303 K; $\mu = 1\text{ M KNO}_3$; aqueous medium

Proton dissociation constants (pKa) :

Ligands	pKa ₁	pKa ₂
GO	8.18 [14]	3.15 [14]
GV	8.21 [20, 21, 24]	3.13 [20, 24]
GL	8.12 [13, 14]	3.15 [13, 14]
GIL	8.16 [14]	3.15 [14]
mal	8.55 [25]	

Stability constants of binary and ternary complexes :

M ^{II}	Binary		Ternary [MLA]			
	Ligand	log K	Ligand L	Ligand A	log β	$\Delta \log K$
Ni ^{II}	GG	4.22 [22]	GG	mal	10.45	+0.68
	GV	4.32 [24]	GV		10.25	+0.38
	GL	4.45 [23]	GL		10.27	+0.21
	GIL	4.54	GIL		10.24	+0.15
	mal	5.55 [25]				
Co ^{II}	GG	3.25 [23]	GG	mal	9.45	+0.86
	GV	3.75	GV		9.54	+0.45
	GL	3.21 [23]	GL		8.85	+0.10
	GIL	3.67	GIL		9.41	+0.40
	mal	5.34 [25]				
Zn ^{II}	GG	3.62 [26]	GG	mal	10.35	+1.03
	GV	4.16 [24]	GV		9.90	+0.04
	GL	3.55 [26]	GL		10.01	+0.76
	GIL	3.77 [26]	GIL		10.16	+0.69
	mal	5.70 [25]				

A) and 'GG' (ligand L) are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. where 'm' is the number of moles of base added per mole of ligand.

Examination of the obtained 1 : 1 : 1 ternary titration curves revealed inflection points at $m = 1$ and $m = 3$, due to the dissociation of three protons from both the ligands. But in the buffer region in the range of $m = 0$ to 1, the ternary titration curves overlapped with the titration curves of the ligand dipeptide and corresponding binary ML system¹². Since this region happens to be the region of carboxylate proton dissociation, it was assumed that the carboxylate group is not involved in metal coordination. After $m = 1$, the existence of a ternary complex is proved by comparison of the mixed ligand titration curve with the binary titration curves, and it has been observed that the ternary curves were located still in a lower pH region than the titration curves of binary

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves for the Ni^{II} : GG : mal at 30 °C and $I = 0.1\text{ M KNO}_3$; A = mal alone, B = Ni^{II} : mal, C = GG alone, D = Ni^{II} : GG, E = Ni^{II} : GG : mal (1 : 1 : 1).

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titration curves for the Co^{II} : GG : mal at 30 °C and $I = 0.1\text{ M KNO}_3$; A = mal alone, B = Zn^{II} : mal (1 : 1), C = GG alone, D = Zn^{II} : GG (1 : 1), E = Zn^{II} : GG : mal (1 : 1 : 1).

indicating the possible coordination of two ligands to the metal ion.

Although the initial step in dipeptide-metal ion complexation is probably interaction between the terminal amino group and the metal ion, it is a well established fact that chelation follows by interaction at the peptide bond also¹³⁻¹⁵. Structural influences in this region of the ligand molecule would preassembly be less pronounced,

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titration curves for the Co^{II} : GG : mal at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $I = 0.1\text{ M KNO}_3$; A = mal alone, B = Co^{II} : mal (1 : 1), C = GC alone, D = Co^{II} : GG (1 : 1), E = Co^{II} : GG : mal (1 : 1 : 1).

because of the strong resonance character of the peptide bond which would tend to stabilize electronic character in this region. Coordination at the peptide bond can theoretically occur either through nitrogen or oxygen, but Rabin¹⁶ has presented evidence that oxygen is the most likely site of initial bonding. Hence it is assumed that the chelate formation is taking place by the coordination of NH group or oxygen atom of peptide bond. While the other ligand maltol forms a stable 5-membered chelate ring simultaneously by coordinating to metal ion through the double bonded oxygen at C-4 position and deprotonated oxygen at C-3 position.

The stability constants of ternary systems (Table 1) also were subjected to refinement using computer program 'BEST' by considering all possible species in solution, with very small error (sig fit = 0.001 to 0.01). The represented stability constants revealed that the thermodynamic stability of binary and ternary metal complexes follows the Irving-William's order. But the observation which is interesting to mention here from the calculation is, the stability constants of binary complexes increased by increasing the alkyl chain length on dipeptide, where as the order of stability constants of ternary complexes is reverse where 'mal' is also binding with metal ion. These variations in the stability constants are discussed in relation to the structural differences in the peptides. The order of binary stability constants follow the order : M^{II} -

$\text{GG} < \text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{-GV} < \text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{-GL} < \text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{-GIL}$ (Table 1). This trend is due to the fact that, substitutions on the carbon adjacent to the peptide nitrogen produce the changes in basicity of ligands through inductive effect¹⁷. This effect boosts with the increase of chain length of alkyl substituent. While in the case of ternary complexes the reverse trend may be attributed to the increasing steric effect by the alkyl chain on peptide group in presence of other coordinated ligand 'mal'.

The higher stability values of ternary systems and the positive $\Delta \log K$ values (Table 1) indicating that the ternary complexes are more stable than their respective binary systems. The positive $\Delta \log K$ values observed in the present study are due to high stability of ternary complexes since in ternary systems both the ligands can mutually influence binding properties of each other through ligand-ligand interactions viz. aliphatic-aromatic hydrophobic interactions¹⁸. In ternary complex formation under study, there is a possibility for dipetides i.e. GG, GV, GL and GIL to act as bidentate ligands involving amine nitrogen and, nitrogen or oxygen of amide moiety and thus rendering COO^- free to enable the coordination of other ligand. This is an accordance with dipeptides character, which shows ambidentate behavior with change in conditions¹⁹.

Distribution diagrams :

The computer programme 'SPE' was used to generate the complete species distribution curves as a function of pH, furnishes the individual species percentage present in the system. The distribution curves of binary and ternary systems with Ni^{II} are given in Figs. 4 and 5 respectively. Binary distribution curves affirm the stable 1 : 1 complex formation (Fig. 4), and ternary complex distribution curves (Fig. 5) reveal that, Ni^{II} is forming stable ternary complexes with maximum extent of percentage than binary complexes as well as other species present in the system.

IR spectral analysis :

The tentative assignment for the selected vibrational bands of the free ligands and their isolated ternary metal complexes is useful for determining the mode of coordination of the ligands (Table 2). The spectral values of free ligands are agreed well with the literature.

Glycylglycine, the simple dipeptide can exist as zwitter ion like an amino acid in both solution and solid state.

Fig. 4. Distribution curves of binary complexes.

Fig. 5. Distribution curves of ternary complexes.

Table 2. Frequencies and the assignment of absorption bands (cm^{-1}) in the infrared spectrum of free ligands and ternary complexes

	$\nu(\text{NH})_{\text{Peptide}}$ and $\nu(\text{NH}_3)$	$\nu(\text{CH}_2)$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{Peptide}}$	
GG	3288 and 3058	2927	1676	
[Ni ^{II} -GG-mal]	3133 _(NH/NH₂)	2469	1595	
GV	3254 and 3072	2960-2598	1690	
[Ni ^{II} -GV-mal]	3154 _(NH/NH₂)	3007	1597	
GL	3260 and 3069	2937-2596	1692	
[Ni ^{II} -GL-mal]	3177 _(NH/NH₂)	2872	1616	
GIL	3258 and 3064	2965-2654	1690	
[Ni ^{II} -GIL-mal]	3179 _(NH/NH₂)	2932	1598	
	$\nu(\text{OH})$	$\nu(\text{CH}_3)$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ ring
mal	3260	2995	1656	1629, 1562
[Ni ^{II} -GG-mal]	-	2966	1595	1568, 1500
[Ni ^{II} -GV-mal]	-	2968	1597	1569, 1499
[Ni ^{II} -GL-mal]	-	2960	1616	1576, 1511
[Ni ^{II} -GIL-mal]	-	2966	1598	1571, 1500

The IR spectra exhibited significant features in $\nu(\text{NH}_3^+)$, $\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ regions^{12,27}. The peaks at 3288 cm^{-1} , 3058 cm^{-1} were assigned to $\nu(\text{NH})_{\text{Peptide}}$ and $\nu(\text{NH})_{\text{NH}_3^+}$ stretching frequencies respectively^{28,29}, and CH group frequency is observed at 2927 cm^{-1} , while peaks at 1676 and 1657 cm^{-1} were assigned to amide group stretching frequencies. Since the GV, GL and GIL possess similar functional groups with change in the alkyl substitution on the carbon, adjacent to the peptide nitrogen, there is a small difference in the stretching frequencies of such functional groups with respect to GG. Table 2 affords the IR spectral values.

The broad band observed at 3260 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum of 'mal', is attributed to the OH stretching. The bands at 3062 cm^{-1} and 2995 cm^{-1} are assigned for aromatic and aliphatic CH vibrations respectively. The band at 1656 cm^{-1} is assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ while the combination bands of the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ are observed at 1629 and 1562 cm^{-1} .

The infrared spectra of ternary complexes (Figs. 6-8) involving the above ligands shows shift in characteristic band positions of ligands, and this can be correlated to ligand chelation with metal ions. The IR spectra of ternary complexes exhibited significant features in $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{COO}^-)$ regions. The IR spectrum of free GG exhibited

Fig. 6. IR spectrum of [Ni^{II}-GV-mal].

Fig. 7. IR spectrum of [Ni^{II}-GL-mal].

Fig. 8. IR spectrum of $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-GIL-mal}]$.

a peak at 3058 cm^{-1} which is attributed to NH_3^+ stretching frequency (the region of $3130\text{--}3030\text{ cm}^{-1}$). But the same peak at isoelectric point observed in the region of $3500\text{--}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to free NH_2 group. In ternary complexes of GG, GV, GL and GIL (Table 2) the IR spectra showed characteristic bands of $\nu(\text{NH})_{\text{NH}_2}$ at 3113, 3117, 3154 and 3179 cm^{-1} respectively, which are lower compared to uncoordinated NH_2 ($3300\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and high compared to νNH_3^+ . In the complexes, NH_3^+ gets deprotonated and binds to metal through the neutral NH_2 group. The shift in stretching frequency of coordinated NH_2 of dipeptide (3113 cm^{-1}) in ternary complex $[\text{Ni-GG-mal}]$ strengthens its strong coordination with metal ion. The IR spectra of other ternary complexes affirm relatively higher stretching frequency values for coordinated NH_2 groups of their respective dipeptides, which can be considered for the decreased coordination strength of terminal NH_2 due to increased steric effect. The $\nu(\text{NH})_{\text{Peptide}}$ peaks expected above 3200 cm^{-1} are shifted upon binding with corresponding ligands and admixed

with amine N-H stretching modes. No considerable shift was observed in the asymmetric stretching vibration of carboxylate groups signifying the non-coordination of carboxylate groups with metal ion.

The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ observed at 1656 cm^{-1} in 'mal' is decreased to 1595, 1597, 1616 and 1598 cm^{-1} in ternary complexes of GG, GV, GL and GIL respectively^{30,31}, confirming participation of the oxygen atom of carbonyl group in bonding. In turn, the disappearance of the peak corresponding to the hydroxyl group of the free ligand $\nu(\text{OH})$ at 3260 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of ternary complexes is the evidence that maltol binds to metal ion through the oxygen atom of the deprotonated hydroxyl group. Thus, it is stated that the comprised complexes have the chelate structure. The comparison of spectra of ternary complexes with ligands also reveals that there is a shift in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ of conjugated double bonds^{4,31} which is due to redistribution of the electron density in chelates resulting a decrease in the frequencies of stretching vibrations³². The observed IR characteristics are in good agreement

with literature data of ternary metal complexes of maltol reported earlier³³⁻³⁵.

UV-Visible studies :

Estimation of an appropriate wavelength range for UV-Vis data acquisition was made in two stages. The UV-Vis data of free ligands was investigated and redetermined. It was shown that charge transfer bands were observed for dipeptides i.e. GG, GV, GL and GIL at 203, 193, 195 and 196 nm respectively, which results from electronic interactions between the amide and carboxylate groups. The charge transfer band involves electron transfer from a carboxylate non-bonding orbital to the amide π^* orbital^{36,37}. The UV-Vis data of free maltol showed maximum absorbance at $\lambda = 276$ nm. In the present study, the UV-Visible spectra have given satisfactory information about the formation of ternary complexes. The Fig. 9 shows the absorption spectra of ternary complexes dissolved in DMSO at room temperature. Spectra are recorded in the UV region with solutions of 1×10^{-4} M concentration. The ternary complexes of Ni^{II}-maltol with GG, GV, GL and GIL exhibited intense absorption bands in the region of 270–350 nm, can be assigned to ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) bands from both maltol and dipeptides.

The spectrum in the visible region showed the $d \rightarrow d^*$ transitions, which apparently have low intensity at low concentrations (1×10^{-4} M) than the charge transfer transitions. Hence the visible spectra of GV and GL ternary complexes (Fig. 9) are recorded at high concentrations (5×10^{-4} M) and observed peaks in the region of 650 to 670 nm suggest a tetrahedral geometry³⁸. Visible spectrum of GV ternary complex showed a peak at 664.80 nm ($\epsilon = 7.4$) with a shoulder which is not recorded. This transition can be assignable to spin allowed ${}^3T_1(P) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F)$ transition and the resulted shoulder which is merged with the peak is due to transition of ${}^3T_2(F) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F)$. The GL ternary complex in the visible region has given two peaks at 663.20 nm ($\epsilon = 26.6$) and 651.40 nm ($\epsilon = 26.2$) for the spin allowed transitions ${}^3T_1(P) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F)$ and ${}^3T_2(F) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F)$ respectively. The third transition in this ternary complexes i.e. ${}^3A_2(F) \leftarrow {}^3T_1(F)$ is not recorded within the range of spectrum. The remaining ternary complexes have followed the same trend.

Mass spectra :

The ESI mass spectra (Figs. 10–12) also have given evidence about the formation of ternary complexes. Molecular ion peaks for GV, GL and GIL ternary complexes with 'mal' and Ni are observed at m/z 357, 371 and 371 respectively, which are in agreement with the molecular weight of the proposed structures. Thus mass spectra further confirm the proposed structures.

Biological activity :

The complexation of biologically important Ni^{II} metal ion with ligands i.e. dipeptides and maltol was further explored with the evaluation of their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis* [MTCC 2063] and Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* [MTCC 1652]. All the ligands and complexes exhibited activity against the tested strains. The ligands showed moderate antibacterial activity (Fig. 13) against two bacterial species, ternary metal complexes of Ni^{II} have showed activity against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli*, but insignificant increase in activity has been observed for Ni^{II} complexes (Fig. 14) for Gram-positive *Bacillus subtilis*. The studies demonstrated that metallation can increase the antibacterial activity than metal free ligand. It has been suggested that⁴⁰, metal chelation reduces the polarity of the metal ion mainly because of the partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possibly the π -electron delocalization occurring within the whole chelate ring system formed during coordination. This process of chelation thus increases the lipophilic nature of the central metal ion, which in turn, favors its permeation through the lipid layer of the membrane⁴¹ thus causing the metal complex to cross the membrane of the microorganism cell wall more effectively and increasing the activity.

Conclusions :

Ternary complex formation is monitored by potentiometric method in aqueous medium and the dissociation constants of compounds and their stability constants of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} metal complexes formed were calculated by BEST programme. The corresponding Ni^{II} ternary complexes were also synthesized and characterized by UV-Visible, IR, and mass spectral data. The potentiometric studies indicated positive $\Delta \log K$ values favoring the formation of ternary complexes with intricate hydrophobic interactions enabling the higher stabilities. The

Fig. 9. UV-Visible spectra of ternary metal complexes.

Fig. 10. Mass spectrum of [Ni-mal-GL] ternary complex.

Fig. 11. Mass spectrum of [Ni-mal-GL] ternary complex.

Fig. 12. Mass spectrum of [Ni-mal-GIL] ternary complex.

Fig. 13. Inhibitory action of GG and mal free ligands on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* organism.

Fig. 14. Inhibitory action of ternary Ni^{II} complexes on the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* organism.

Fig. 15. Energy minimized structures of the most stable isomers of ternary complexes.

spectral characterization of Ni^{II} solid complexes with title compounds infers the mode of bonding and structural

changes in ligand upon coordination with metal ion. The electron absorption spectral results supported tetrahedral geometry for the ternary complexes. The results from solution and solid state studies unraveled the information about the coordination sites available in both the ligands and the coordination sites actually involved in bonding with metal ions. It can be concluded that COO⁻ is not involved in bonding as its participation increases the steric hindrance in ternary complexes. The formation of ternary complexes studied keeping in the biological importance of dipeptides and maltol, indicated enhanced anti-bacterial activity. The structures of ternary complexes (Fig. 15) under present study have been assigned based on the results obtained. The most stable isomers with minimum energy are given in Fig. 15, and the energy minimization was done by using "Hyper Chem" software.

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